

FRIES AND FRIEDEL-CRAFTS' REACTIONS WITH METHYL 2:4-DI-HYDROXY-5-SUBSTITUTED BENZOATES AND SYNTHESIS OF 4-SUBSTITUTED 2-ACYLRESORCINOLS

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Several 2-propionyl- and 2-butyryl-4-substituted resorcinols have been synthesised and condensed with ethyl acetoacetate.

In continuation of our work (this *Journal*, 1952, 29, 351, 915; 1953, 30, 373; 1954, 31, 600; 1955, 32, 529) on the Fries migration of the esters of 5-substituted β -resorcylic acids and their methyl esters and subsequent synthesis of 4-substituted 2-acylresorcinols, several 2-propionyl- and 2-butyryl-4-substituted resorcinols are described in this communication.

Methyl 5-ethyl-, 5-bromo-, 5-chloro-2:4-dipropionoxybenzoates (I: R = -COEt; X = Et, Br or Cl) afforded on migration below 130°, methyl 2:4-dihydroxy-3-propionyl-5-substituted benzoates and the corresponding acids (II: R = -COEt; R₁ = Me and H; X = Et, Br or Cl), hydrolysis occurring during the migration. The migration at higher temperature favours the hydrolysis of the keto-ester formed. The keto-esters (II: R = -COEt; R₁ = Me) on alkaline hydrolysis furnished the keto-acids, identical with the same, obtained as migration products. The keto-acids on decarboxylation afforded 4-ethyl-, 4-bromo-, and 4-chloro-2-propionyl-resorcinols (III: R = -COEt; X = Et, Br or Cl). For comparison, these were synthesised by starting from 6-ethyl-, 6-bromo- and 6-chloro-7-methylcoumarins by Limaye's Nidhone process (*Ber.*, 1932, 65, 375; 1934, 67, 12; *Rasayanam*, 1937, 80; 1939, 191 et seq), and were found identical.

The Friedel-Crafts propionylation of 5-substituted methyl β -resorcylic acids and the corresponding acids yielded the ketonic products, identical with the migration products.

The Friedel-Crafts butyrylation of methyl 2:4-dihydroxy-5-substituted benzoates or the corresponding acids afforded the keto-esters and/or acids [II: R = -COPrⁿ; X = Et, Br or Cl; R₁ = Me and/or H], 4-ethyl-, 4-bromo- and 4-chloro-2-butyrylresorcinols being obtained from the keto-acids by decarboxylation. The same keto-acids were also obtained independently by the Fries migration of the propionyl and butyryl derivatives of 5-bromo- and 5-chloro- β -resorcylic acids.

4-Substituted 2-acylresorcinols smoothly underwent the Pechmann condensation with ethyl acetoacetate giving rise to the keto-coumarins^o [IV: R = -COEt or -COPrⁿ;

X=Et, Br or Cl], identical with the Fries migration products of the corresponding 7-acyloxy-6- substituted 4-methylcoumarins, thus establishing the structures of all the ketonic products described before.

EXPERIMENTAL

Methyl 2:4-Dipropionyloxy-5-ethylbenzoate (I : R = COEt ; X = Et)

The compound (I : X = Et) was prepared by heating methyl 2:4-dihydroxy-5-ethylbenzoate (4 g.), propionic anhydride (6 c.c.) and H_2SO_4 (conc., drop) on a water-bath for 2 hours. The product, isolated as usual, crystallised from dilute alcohol in colorless plates, m.p. 89° (3 g.). (Found : C, 62.0 ; H, 6.4. $C_{18}H_{20}O_6$ requires C, 62.3 ; H, 6.5%). It is insoluble in alkali and does not respond to EtOH- $FeCl_3$ colour test.

Fries Migration of (I : R = -COEt ; X = Et).—The propionyloxy-ester (3 g., 1 M) and anhydrous aluminium chloride were intimately mixed and heated at $110-20^\circ$ for an hour ($CaCl_2$ guard-tube). The cold reaction mixture was then decomposed with crushed ice and HCl (conc., 5 c.c.). The solid obtained was filtered and treated with sodium bicarbonate solution (5%), when a part of it dissolved with effervescence. The bicarbonate-insoluble keto-ester crystallised from alcohol in yellow needles, m.p. 91° (0.8 g.). (Found : C, 61.6 ; H, 6.3. $C_{18}H_{18}O_5$ requires C, 61.9 ; H, 6.4%).

The keto-acid, obtained on acidifying the bicarbonate solution, crystallised from dilute ethanol in colorless needles, m.p. 183° (efferv.) (0.6 g.). (Found : C, 60.4 ; H, 5.7. $C_{12}H_{14}O_5$ requires C, 60.5 ; H, 5.9%).

The *dibenzoyl* derivative of the keto-ester, prepared by benzoyl chloride-pyridine method, crystallised from alcohol in colorless needles, m.p. 114° . (Found : C, 70.2 ; H, 5.1. $C_{27}H_{24}O_7$ requires C, 70.4 ; H, 5.2%).

Friedel-Crafts' Propionylation of (I : R = H ; X = Et).—Methyl 2:4-dihydroxy-5-ethylbenzoate (2.5 g.) and propionic anhydride (2.5 c.c.) were added to a cold solution of aluminium chloride (3.5 g.) in dry nitrobenzene (30 c.c.) with shaking and cooling. The mixture was left at $25-30^\circ$ for 20 hours and then heated at 105° for 4 hours ($CaCl_2$ guard-tube). On decomposition with ice and HCl (conc., 5 c.c.) and removal of nitrobenzene by steam-distillation, the solid obtained was treated with 5% NaOH solution; the yellow alkaline filtrate on acidification furnished a solid having no sharp m.p. It was therefore treated with bicarbonate solution (5%) and the keto ester and acid were separated and crystallised as before. Their mixed melting points with the migration products obtained before remained undepressed.

Hydrolysis of (II : R = -COEt ; X = Et ; $R_1 = Me$) (0.8 g.) by 10% NaOH solution (20 c.c.) at room temperature for 24 hours afforded on acidification 2:4-dihydroxy-3-propionyl-5-ethylbenzoic acid which crystallised from dilute ethanol, m.p. 183° (efferv.), identical with the same acid obtained before.

Formation of 4-Ethyl-2-propionylresorcinol (III : R = -COEt ; X = Et).—The keto-acid (1 g.) in water (80 c.c.), acetic acid (1 c.c.) and a few drops of HCl (conc.) were refluxed on a sand-bath for 20 hours and then filtered hot. The filtrate on cooling and diluting afforded a yellow solid, which crystallised from water in needles, m.p. 102° (0.3 g.).

undepressed with the hydrolysis product of 8-propionyl-7-hydroxy-6-ethyl-4-methylcoumarin (*vide infra*). (Found: C, 67.9; H, 7.2. $C_{11}H_{14}O_3$ requires C, 68.0; H, 7.2%). It developed a green colour with EtOH-FeCl₃ and a yellow colour with alkali. It is easily soluble in alcohol and in other common organic solvents.

8-Propionyl-7-hydroxy-6-ethyl-4-methylcoumarin (IV: R = -COEt; X = Et).—Ethyl-2-propionylresorcinol (0.5 g.) was mixed with ethyl acetoacetate (1.0 g.) in presence of H₂SO₄ (80%, 3 c.c.) in cold and then left overnight at room temperature. On treating with ice-cold water, a yellow solid was obtained which crystallised from alcohol in lustrous yellow needles, m.p. 111°, undepressed with the Fries migration product of 7-propionoxy-6-ethyl-4-methylcoumarin.

7-Propionoxy-6-ethyl-4-methylcoumarin was prepared by heating 7-hydroxy-6-ethyl-4-methylcoumarin (5 g.) with propionic anhydride (6 c.c.) in presence of H₂SO₄ (conc., drop) for 2 hours. On working it up as usual, it crystallised from ethanol in colorless needles, m.p. 154° (4 g.). (Found: C, 69.0; H, 6.0. $C_{15}H_{18}O_4$ requires C, 69.2; H, 6.2%). It did not develop any colour with alcoholic ferric chloride.

Fries Migration.—An intimate mixture of the above propionoxy-coumarin (3 g., 1 M) and anhydrous aluminium chloride (5 g., 3.3 M) was baked at 140-50° for an hour (CaCl₂ guard-tube); fumes of HCl gas evolved vigorously at 125°. On working up as before, the product obtained was crystallised from ethanol in yellow shining needles, m.p. 111° (1.2 g.). (Found: C, 69.1; H, 6.1. $C_{15}H_{18}O_4$ requires C, 69.2; H, 6.2%). It dissolved in alkali with non-fluorescent yellow colour and developed a brown colour with EtOH-FeCl₃.

The *acetoxy* derivative, prepared by acetic anhydride-pyridine method, crystallised from ethanol in colorless lustrous needles, m.p. 137°. (Found: C, 67.4; H, 6.0. $C_{17}H_{20}O_5$ requires C, 67.5; H, 6.0%).

The *benzoyloxy* derivative, prepared by benzoyl chloride-pyridine method, crystallised from dilute ethanol in colorless needles, m.p. 130°. (Found: C, 72.3; H, 5.4. $C_{22}H_{20}O_5$ requires C, 72.5; H, 5.5%). The *semicarbazone*, prepared by usual method, crystallised from alcohol in fibrous needles, m.p. 208° (decomp.). [Found: N, 13.0. $C_{16}H_{18}O_4N_2$ requires N, 13.2%].

Hydrolysis of the Keto-coumarin (IV: R = -COEt; X = Et).—The keto-coumarin (1 g.) in 10% NaOH (25 c.c.) was refluxed on a sand-bath for 2 hours and then filtered hot. On acidifying the cold filtrate, a puffy solid was obtained. It crystallised from water in yellow needles, m.p. 102°, undepressed with the sample obtained before.

Friedel-Crafts' Butyrylation of Methyl 2:4-dihydroxy-5-ethylbenzoate.—Methyl 2:4-dihydroxy-5-ethylbenzoate (3 g.) was added in small instalments to a cold solution of aluminium chloride (4.2 g.) in dry nitrobenzene (40 c.c.). *n*-Butyric anhydride (3 c.c.) was then added slowly with cooling. The mixture was left overnight at room temperature and then heated at 100-105° for 4 hours (CaCl₂ guard-tube). It was then cooled and worked up as before. The solid obtained after steam-distillation of nitrobenzene was treated with bicarbonate solution as before. The keto-ester crystallised from ethanol in straw-coloured needles, m.p. 66° (0.8 g.). (Found: C, 63.1; H, 6.6. $C_{14}H_{16}O_5$ requires C, 63.2; H, 6.8%). The keto-acid crystallised from dilute ethanol in fibrous

needles, m.p. 181 (efferv.) (0.6 g.) (Found: C, 61.8; H, 6.3. $C_{13}H_{16}O_5$ requires C, 61.9; H, 6.4%). The keto-ester developed a purple colour and the acid, a violet colour with $EtOH-FeCl_3$. Both exhibited a yellow colour with alkali.

The *dibenzoyl* derivative of the keto-ester crystallised from alcohol in colorless needles; m.p. 108°. (Found: C, 70.7; H, 5.4. $C_{28}H_{26}O_7$ requires C, 70.9; H, 5.5%).

Hydrolysis: Formation of 2:4-Dihydroxy-3-butyryl-5-ethylbenzoic Acid.—The ester (0.6 g.) in 10% NaOH (20 c.c.) was heated on a water-bath for an hour and then kept overnight at room temperature. The solid obtained on acidification was treated with bicarbonate solution (5%). The filtrate, on acidification afforded a solid, which crystallised from dilute ethanol, m.p. 181 (efferv.), mixed melting point with the keto-acid obtained before remaining undepressed.

Decarboxylation of the keto-acid (II: $R = -COPr^a$; $X = Et$; $R_1 = H$) (0.8 g.) with acidulated water as before gave 4-ethyl-2-butyrylresorcinol (III: $R = -COPr^a$; $X = Et$). It crystallised from water in yellow needles, m.p. 80° (yield 25%), identical with the hydrolysis product of 8-butyryl-7-hydroxy-6-ethyl-4-methylcoumarin. (Found: C, 69.1; H, 7.5. $C_{12}H_{16}O_5$ requires C, 69.2; H, 7.7%). It showed a green colour with $EtOH-FeCl_3$.

The *Pechmann condensation* of (III: $R = -COPr^a$; $X = Et$) (0.5 g.) with ethyl acetoacetate (1 g.) in presence of H_2SO_4 (30%, 3 c.c.) as before, afforded 8-butyryl-7-hydroxy-6-ethyl-4-methylcoumarin, which crystallised from ethanol in yellow needles, m.p. 110°, identical with the coumarin obtained by the Fries migration of 7-butyroxy-6-ethyl-4-methylcoumarin.

7-Butyroxy-6-ethyl-4-methylcoumarin, prepared by heating the hydroxy-coumarin (5 g.); *n*-butyric anhydride (6 c.c.) and H_2SO_4 (conc., drop) as before, crystallised from ethanol in shining needles, m.p. 125° (4 g.). (Found: C, 70.0; H, 6.5. $C_{16}H_{18}O_4$ requires C, 70.1; H, 6.6%).

Fries Migration.—The butyroxy-coumarin (3 g., 1 M) and aluminium chloride (5.5 g., 3.3 M) were heated at 140-50°. On working up as before, the product crystallised from ethanol in yellow needles, m.p. 110° (1.2 g.). (Found: C, 70.2; H, 6.4. $C_{16}H_{18}O_4$ requires C, 70.1; H, 6.6%). It showed a reddish brown colour with $EtOH-FeCl_3$. The *acetoxy* derivative of the keto-coumarin crystallised from methanol in colorless needles, m.p. 114° (Found: C, 68.1; H, 6.2. $C_{16}H_{20}O_5$ requires C, 68.4; H, 6.3%).

The *oxime* crystallised from alcohol in colorless needles, m.p. 167° (decomp.). (Found: N, 4.6. $C_{16}H_{18}O_4N$ requires N, 4.8%).

Formation of 4-Ethyl-2-butyrylresorcinol (III: $R = -COPr^a$; $X = Et$).—The keto-coumarin (0.8 g.) on alkaline hydrolysis as before afforded a product which crystallised from hot water in yellow needles, m.p. 80° (0.2 g.), mixed melting point with the sample obtained before being undepressed.

Methyl 2:4-Dipropionoxy-5-bromobenzoate (I: $R = -COEt$; $X = Br$)

The compound (I: $X = Br$) was obtained by heating methyl 5-bromo- β -resorcyate (5 g.), propionic anhydride (7 c.c.) and H_2SO_4 (conc., drop) as before. It crystallised from acetic acid in colorless plates, m.p. 122° (3.5 g.). (Found: Br, 22.0. $C_{14}H_{16}O_6Br$ requires Br, 22.3%).

Fries Migration of (I:R = -COEt; X=Br).—(i). The propionoxy-ester (3 g., 1 M) and AlCl_3 (4.5 g., 3.3 M) were heated at $125\text{--}30^\circ$ for an hour, HCl gas evolving at 100° . On working it up as before, the product obtained was found to be a mixture. It was treated with sodium bicarbonate solution (5%), when it partly dissolved with effervescence. The bicarbonate-insoluble portion crystallised from alcohol in yellow silky needles, m.p. 120° (0.8 g.). (Found: Br, 26.2. $\text{C}_{11}\text{H}_{11}\text{O}_2\text{Br}$ requires Br, 26.4%).

The bicarbonate solution on acidification provided a pale yellow puffy solid, which crystallised from dilute alcohol in needles, m.p. $219\text{--}20^\circ$ (efferv.) (0.6 g.). (Found: Br, 27.4. $\text{C}_{10}\text{H}_9\text{O}_2\text{Br}$ requires Br, 27.7%). The keto-ester developed a red colour and the acid, a purple colour with alcoholic ferric chloride.

(ii). The above migration at $160\text{--}70^\circ$ gave only the keto-acid, identified by its mixed m.p. with an authentic sample.

(iii). The above migration, when carried out using nitrobenzene (40 c.c.) as a solvent at room temperature for 24 hours or at 100° for an hour, also gave the same keto-ester and acid, identified by their mixed m. p. with authentic samples.

Methyl 5-bromo- β -resorcylate was propionated by propionic anhydride under the conditions of the Friedel-Crafts reaction as before. The keto-ester and the acid obtained were found identical with the migration products.

The *dibenzoyl* derivative of the keto-ester crystallised from alcohol in colorless needles, m.p. 129° . (Found: Br, 15.4. $\text{C}_{25}\text{H}_{19}\text{O}_7\text{Br}$ requires Br, 15.7 %).

The *semicarbazone* crystallised from dilute alcohol in colorless fibrous needles, m.p. 196° (decomp.). (Found: N, 11.4. $\text{C}_{12}\text{H}_{11}\text{O}_5\text{N}_3\text{Br}$ requires N, 11.7 %).

Hydrolysis of the keto-ester (II: R = -COEt; X = Br; R_1 = Me) (1 g.) was carried out as before. The acid (II: R = -COEt; X = Br; R_1 = H) obtained was crystallised from dilute alcohol in needles, m.p. 219° (efferv.), undepressed with the same obtained by the Fries migration.

2-Hydroxy-4-propionoxy-5-bromobenzoic acid, prepared by heating 5-bromo β -resorcyclic acid (5 g.) with propionic anhydride (6.5 c.c.) and pyridine (2 drops) at 100° for 4 hours as before, crystallised from dilute alcohol in buff-coloured needles, m.p. 166° (2.5 g.). (Found: Br, 27.5. $\text{C}_{10}\text{H}_9\text{O}_5\text{Br}$ requires Br, 27.7 %). It developed a violet colour with $\text{EtOH}\cdot\text{FeCl}_3$.

Fries Migration.—The above propionoxy-acid (3 g., 1 M) and AlCl_3 (4.8 g., 3.3 M) were heated together at $165\text{--}70^\circ$ for an hour and worked up as before. The keto-acid obtained was purified by bicarbonate solution (5%) treatment. It crystallised from dilute alcohol in needles, m.p. 219° (efferv.) (1 g.); mixed m.p. with the same acid obtained above remained undepressed.

The migration at a higher temperature gave poor yields of the keto-acid.

Friedel-Crafts' propionylation of 5-bromo- β -resorcyclic acid was carried out as before. 2:4-Dihydroxy-3-propionyl-5-bromobenzoic acid was obtained, m. p. 219° (efferv.).

The *methyl ester*, prepared by esterifying it as before, was identical with the migration product.

Formation of 4-Bromo-2-propionylresorcinol (II: R = -COEt; X = Br).—The keto-acid (0.5 g.) was decarboxylated as before. The product crystallised from hot water as yellow needles, m.p. 115° (0.15 g.). (Found: Br, 32.4. C₉H₉O₃Br requires Br, 32.7%). It showed a green colour with EtOH-FeCl₃.

8-Propionyl-7-hydroxy-6-bromo-4-methylcoumarin (IV: R = -COEt; X = Br) was obtained by the Pechmann condensation of 4-bromo-2-propionylresorcinol with ethyl acetoacetate as before. It crystallised from acetic acid in lustrous needles, m. p. 198° undepressed with the keto-coumarin obtained by the Fries migration of 7-propionoxy-6-bromo-4-methylcoumarin.

7-Propionoxy-6-bromo-4-methylcoumarin crystallised from alcohol in colorless lustrous needles, m.p. 128° (3 g.). (Found: Br, 25.3. C₁₃H₁₁O₄Br requires Br, 25.7%).

Fries Migration.—The above propionoxy-coumarin (3 g., 1M) and AlCl₃ (anhyd., 5 g., 3.3 M) were heated at 150° for an hour. On working up as before, the product crystallised from acetic acid in yellow needles, m.p. 198° (1.2 g.), identical with the keto-coumarin obtained by the Pechmann condensation. (Found: Br, 26.0. C₁₃H₁₁O₄Br requires Br, 25.7%). It developed a reddish brown colour with EtOH-FeCl₃ and dissolved in alkali with a non-fluorescent yellow colour.

The *acetoxy* derivative crystallised from ethanol in colorless needles, m.p. 166° (Found: Br, 22.4. C₁₃H₁₃O₅Br requires Br, 22.7%).

The *benzoyloxy* derivative crystallised from ethanol in needles, m. p. 159°. (Found: Br, 19.4. C₂₀H₁₁O₅Br requires Br, 19.3%).

The *oxime* crystallised from dilute ethanol in colorless granules, m. p. 216° (decomp.). (Found: N, 4.0. C₁₃H₁₂O₄NBr requires N, 4.3 %).

Friedel-Crafts' Butyrylation of Methyl 2:4-Dihydroxy-5-bromobenzoate.—The bromo-ester (3 g.) and *n*-butyric anhydride (2.5 c.c.) were added to the solution of AlCl₃ (4 g.) in nitrobenzene (30 c. c.) and heated as before. On working up as usual the keto-ester crystallised from alcohol in yellow needles, m.p. 107° (0.8 g.). (Found Br, 25.4. C₁₂H₁₁O₅Br requires Br, 25.2%). The keto-acid crystallised from dilute alcohol in needles, m.p. 211° (efferv.). (Found: Br, 26.3. C₁₁H₁₁O₅Br requires Br, 26.4%).

Both the keto-ester and the acid showed colour reaction with EtOH-FeCl₃.

Friedel-Crafts' butyrylation of 5-bromo-β-resorcylic acid as above gave the same keto-acid (II: R = -COPrⁿ; X = Br; R₁ = H).

The keto-ester (II: R = -COPrⁿ; X = Br; R = Me) on hydrolysis as before furnished the keto-acid, identical with one obtained above.

The *oxime* of the keto-ester crystallised from dilute alcohol in colorless granules, m.p. 166° (decomp.). (Found: N, 4.0. C₁₂H₁₁O₅NBr requires N, 4.2%).

Fries Migration of 2-Hydroxy-4-O-butyryl-5-bromobenzoic Acid.—*2-Hydroxy-4-butyroxy-5-bromobenzoic acid*, prepared by heating 5-bromo-β-resorcylic acid with *n*-butyric anhydride and pyridine as before, crystallised from dilute alcohol in colorless needles, m.p. 146°. (Found: Br, 26.2. C₁₁H₁₁O₅Br requires Br, 26.4%).

The above butyroxy-acid (3 g.) was heated with AlCl₃ (5 g.) at 170-75° for an hour and then worked up as before. The keto-acid obtained crystallised from dilute alcohol in needles, m.p. 211° (efferv.).

The keto-acid (II: R = -COPrⁿ; X = Br; R₁ = H) on decarboxylation as before, afforded a product which crystallised from water in yellow fibrous needles, m.p. 108-109°, identified as 4-bromo-2-butyrylresorcinol (III: R = -COPrⁿ; X = Br). (Found: Br, 30.6. C₁₀H₁₁O₃Br requires Br, 30.9%). It showed a green colour with EtOH-FeCl₃. It condensed with ethyl acetoacetate in presence of H₂SO₄ (80%) as before, yielding 8-butyryl-7-hydroxy-6-bromo-4-methylcoumarin. It crystallised from alcohol in yellow needles, m.p. 157° (3 g.), identical with the migration product of 7-butyroxy 6-bromo-4-methylcoumarin.

8-Butyryl-7-hydroxy-6-bromo-4-methylcoumarin (IV: R = -COPrⁿ; X = Br).—7-Butyroxy-6-bromo-4-methylcoumarin, prepared as before, crystallised from alcohol in colorless shining plates, m.p. 120° (4 g.). (Found: Br, 24.2. C₁₄H₁₃O₄Br requires Br, 24.6%).

The butyroxy-coumarin (3 g., 1 M) was heated with AlCl₃ (4.5 g., 3.3 M) at 145-50 for an hour and worked up as before. The solid obtained was crystallised from alcohol in glistening yellow needles, m.p. 156° (1.2 g.), identical with the keto-coumarin obtained before by the Pechmann condensation. (Found: Br, 24.2. C₁₄H₁₃O₄Br requires Br, 24.6%). It developed a reddish brown colour with EtOH-FeCl₃ and dissolved in alkali with a non-fluorescent yellow colour.

The acetoxy derivative crystallised from alcohol in colorless needles, m.p. 128°. (Found: Br, 22.5. C₁₃H₁₂O₃Br requires Br, 21.8%).

The benzoyloxy derivative crystallised from alcohol in colorless lustrous cubes, m.p. 151°. (Found: Br, 18.4. C₂₁H₁₇O₃Br requires Br, 18.6%).

The semi carbazone, prepared as usual, crystallised from dilute alcohol in colorless granules, m.p. 231° (decomp.). (Found: N, 10.5. C₁₀H₁₀O₄N₂Br requires N, 10.9%).

Methyl 2:4-Dipropionyloxy-5-chlorobenzoate (I: R = -COEt; X = Cl)

For sake of brevity, the experimental details have been omitted in this part, as they are generally identical with the corresponding bromo compounds, already described.

The compound (I: R = -COEt; X = Cl) crystallised from alcohol in colorless lustrous needles, m.p. 114°. (Found: Cl, 11.0. C₁₄H₁₃O₆Cl requires Cl, 11.3%).

Fries Migration of (I, R = -COEt; X = Cl).—A mixture of the propionyloxy-ester (3 g.) and AlCl₃ (4.5 g.) was heated at 125-30° for an hour and worked up as before. The acid and ester were separated by bicarbonate treatment. The ester crystallised from acetic acid in yellow fleecy needles, m.p. 107° (0.9 g.). (Found: Cl, 13.6. C₁₁H₁₁O₆Cl requires Cl, 13.7%). The keto-acid crystallised from dilute alcohol in pale yellow needles, m.p. 206° (efferv.) (p. 5 g.). (Found: Cl, 14.3. C₁₀H₉O₅Cl requires Cl, 14.5%).

Both the keto-ester and the acid showed colour reaction with alcoholic ferric chloride. The keto-ester on alkaline hydrolysis as before afforded the acid, identical with the keto-acid obtained above.

Friedel-Crafts' propionylation of methyl 2:4-dihydroxy-5-chlorobenzoate and the corresponding acid (3 g.) with propionic anhydride (2.5 c.c.) under similar conditions described for the bromo compounds yielded the keto-ester (II: R = -COEt; X = Cl; R₁ = Me) and the corresponding keto-acid, identical with the migration products.

The *dibenzoyl* of the keto-ester crystallised from alcohol in colorless lustrous plates, m.p. 124°. (Found: Cl, 7.3. $C_{25}H_{19}O_7Cl$ requires Cl, 7.6%).

The *semicarbazone* of the keto-ester crystallised from dilute alcohol in colorless needles, m.p. 198° (decomp.). (Found: N, 13.0. $C_{12}H_{14}O_5N_3Cl$ requires N, 13.3%).

Fries Migration of 2-Hydroxy-4-O-propionyl-5-chlorobenzoic Acid.—2-Hydroxy-4-propionoxy-5-chlorobenzoic acid, prepared as before, crystallised from dilute alcohol in silvery flakes, m.p. 155°. (Found: Cl, 14.4. $C_{10}H_8O_5Cl$ requires Cl, 14.5 %).

The above propionoxy-acid (2.5 g.) was mixed with $AlCl_3$ (5 g.) and heated at 165° for an hour. It was worked up as before. The solid obtained crystallised from dilute alcohol in needles, m.p. 207° (efferv.) (0.8 g.), undepressed with the sample obtained before.

The *methyl ester* of the above keto-acid, prepared by esterification, crystallised from acetic acid in yellow needles, m. p. 107°, identical with the migration product.

The *decarboxylation of the keto-acid* by acidulated water, as before, gave 4-chloro-2-propionylresorcinol, (III: R = -COEt; X=Cl), crystallised from dilute alcohol in yellow needles, m.p. 107°, undepressed on admixture with the same, synthesised from 8-propionyl-7-hydroxy-6-chloro-4-methylcoumarin. (Found: Cl, 17.6. Calc. for $C_{17}H_{16}O_4Cl$: Cl, 17.7%). It showed a green colour with $EtOH-FeCl_3$ and dissolved in alkali with a yellow colour.

The *Pechmann condensation* of (III: R = -COEt; X=Cl) (0.5 g.) with ethyl acetoacetate (1.5 g.) in presence of H_2SO_4 (80%, 4 c.c.) as before gave the keto-coumarin (IV: R = -COEt; X=Cl). It crystallised from alcohol in yellow needles, m. p. 181° (0.4 g.), undepressed with the migration product of 7-propionoxy-6-chloro-4-methylcoumarin:

7-Propionoxy-6-chloro-4-methylcoumarin, prepared as before, was crystallised from ethanol in colorless needles, m. p. 111°. (Found: Cl, 13.1. $C_{13}H_{11}O_4Cl$ requires Cl, 13.3 %).

Fries Migration.—The propionoxy-coumarin (3 g.) and $AlCl_3$ (5 g.) were heated at 140-50° for an hour and worked up as before. The product crystallised from a mixture of alcohol and a few drops of acetic acid in yellow needles, m. p. 181° (1.2 g.), undepressed with the same keto-coumarin obtained before. (Found: Cl, 13.1. $C_{13}H_{11}O_4Cl$ requires Cl, 13.3%). It developed a reddish brown colour with alcoholic ferric chloride.

The *acetoxy* derivative of the keto-coumarin crystallised from dilute alcohol in colorless needles, m.p. 168°. (Found: Cl, 11.4. $C_{15}H_{13}O_5Cl$ requires Cl, 11.5%).

The *benzoyloxy* derivative crystallised from alcohol in clusters of colorless needles, m. p. 171°. (Found: Cl, 9.4. $C_{20}H_{15}O_5Cl$ requires Cl, 9.6%).

The *semicarbazone* crystallised from alcohol in pale yellow needles, m. p. 216° (decomp.). (Found: N, 12.6. $C_{14}H_{14}O_4N_3Cl$ requires Cl, 12.9%).

The keto-coumarin on hydrolysis as before gave 4-chloro-2-propionylresorcinol (III: R = -COEt; X=Cl). It crystallised from dilute alcohol in yellow needles, m. p. 107°

The *dibenzoyl* derivative of (III: R = -COEt; X=Cl) crystallised from alcohol in colorless plates, m.p. 120° (Found: Cl, 8.4. $C_{23}H_{17}O_5Cl$ requires Cl, 8.7%).

Friedel-Crafts' butyrylation of (I: R=H; X=Cl) and the corresponding acid as before furnished the keto-ester (II: R = -COCPrⁿ; X = Cl; R₁ = Me) and the corresponding keto-acid. The keto-ester crystallised from acetic acid in yellow silky needles, m.p. 100°. (Found: Cl, 13.2. C₁₂H₁₃O₅Cl requires Cl, 13.0%) The keto-acid crystallised from dilute alcohol in pale yellow needles, m. p. 202° (efferv.). (Found: Cl, 13.5. C₁₁H₁₁O₅Cl requires Cl, 13.7%). They showed red colour with EtOH-FeCl₃.

The *dibenzoyl* derivative of the keto-ester crystallised from alcohol in colorless truncated needles, m.p. 101°. (Found: Cl, 7.1. C₂₆H₂₁O₇Cl requires Cl, 7.4%).

The *oxime* of the keto-ester crystallised from dilute alcohol in shining needles, m.p. 167° (decomp.). (Found N, 4.7. C₁₂H₁₄O₅NCl requires N, 4.9%).

The keto-ester on alkaline hydrolysis as before gave the keto-acid (II: R = -COPrⁿ; X = Cl; R₁ = H), identical with the migration product.

Fries Migration of 2-Hydroxy-4-O-butyryl-5-chlorobenzoic Acid.—*2-Hydroxy-4-butyroxy-5-chlorobenzoic acid* was crystallised from dilute alcohol in silvery flakes, m. p. 145°. (Found: Cl, 13.8. C₁₁H₁₁O₅Cl requires Cl, 13.7%).

The above butyroxy-acid (3 g.) was heated with AlCl₃ (4.8 g.) at 145° for an hour and worked up as before. The product crystallised from dilute alcohol in pale yellow needles, m.p. 203° (efferv.), undepressed with the keto-acid obtained before.

The keto-acid was decarboxylated to 4-chloro-2-butyrylresorcinol (III: R = -COPrⁿ; X=Cl) as before. It crystallised from dilute alcohol in yellow needles, m.p. 115°, undepressed with the hydrolysis product of 8-butyryl-7-hydroxy-6-chloro-1-methylcoumarin (IV: R = -COPrⁿ; X=Cl). (Found: Cl, 16.2. C₁₆H₁₁O₅Cl requires Cl, 16.6%). It showed a green colour with EtOH-FeCl₃.

4-Chloro-2-butyrylresorcinol condensed with ethyl acetoacetate as before, furnishing the keto-coumarin (IV: R = -COPrⁿ; X=Cl), which crystallised from alcohol in yellow fibrous needles, m. p. 153°, identical with the same obtained by the Fries migration.

7-Butyroxy-6-chloro 4-methylcoumarin crystallised from alcohol in colorless lustrous plates, m.p. 119°. (Found: Cl, 12.4. C₁₄H₁₃O₄Cl requires Cl, 12.7%).

The above butyroxy-coumarin (3 g.) was heated with AlCl₃ (4.8 g.) at 145-50° for one hour and worked up as before. The product crystallised from alcohol in yellow needles, m.p. 153° (1 g.), undepressed with the same keto-coumarin obtained before. (Found: Cl, 12.5. C₁₄H₁₃O₄Cl requires Cl, 12.7%). It showed a red colour with EtOH-FeCl₃.

The *acetoxy* derivative crystallised from ethanol in colorless needles, m. p. 139°. (Found: Cl, 10.9. C₁₈H₁₅O₅Cl requires Cl, 11.0%).

The *benzoyloxy* derivative crystallised from ethanol in colorless lustrous cubes, m.p. 144°. (Found: Cl, 9.1. C₂₁H₁₇O₅Cl requires Cl, 9.2%).

The *oxime* crystallised from alcohol in colorless needles, m. p. 197° (decomp.). (Found: N, 4.4. $C_{11}H_{14}O_4NCl$ requires N, 4.7%).

The keto-coumarin (IV: R = -COPrⁿ; X=Cl) was hydrolysed with sodium hydroxide (12%) as before and 4-chloro-2-butyrylresorcinol (III: R = -COPrⁿ; X=Cl) was obtained. It crystallised from dilute alcohol in yellow needles, m.p. 115°.

The *dibenzoate* of (III: R = -COPrⁿ; X=Cl) crystallised from alcohol in colorless plates, m.p. 123°. (Found: Cl, 8.1. $C_{21}H_{18}O_5Cl$ requires Cl, 8.4%).

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